

Article

MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF PROCESSES IN A CYLINDRICAL COMBUSTION CHAMBER IN ANSYS FLUENT SOFTWARE PACKAGE

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M.M. Hamdamov¹, O.M. Begimov¹, Sh.A. Ravshanov¹

¹National Research University TIAME, Tashkent, 100000, Uzbekistan

*Corresponding author: mmhamdamov@mail.ru

Abstract. When mathematically modeling gas combustion processes within the ANSYS Fluent software package, the main problem is the choice of a turbulence model. As part of the work, standard and modified methods were tested to describe turbulence models, Spalart-Allmaras model, $k-\epsilon$ model and RNG model to describe the mixing and combustion of methane according to the Arrhenius law in a cylindrical chamber. The calculations used the control volume method embedded in ANSYS Fluent, where the velocity and pressure fields are related by the PISO algorithm. Satisfactory agreement between the calculation and experimental results was obtained when implementing the modified models based on axial distributions of temperature and longitudinal velocity.

Keywords: cylindrical chamber, ANSYS Fluent, PISO algorithm, Spalart-Allmaras model, Arrhenius law, RNG model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, software products are actively used in scientific and technical organizations and universities to simulate various processes. Their use has become relevant in the study of thermal processes observed in engineering and technology. The development of fire played a key role in the development of civilization. Fire opened up for people the possibility of thermal processing of food and heating of homes, and subsequently - the development of metallurgy, energy and the creation of new, more advanced tools and technologies that use solid, liquid and gaseous substances as fuel. Control of combustion processes underlies the creation of modern engines for cars, airplanes, ships and rockets, where combustion of pre-mixed and unmixed mutually reacting substances is practiced.

Combustion is a complex physicochemical process of converting starting substances into combustion products in the course of chemical reactions accompanied by intense heat release. Its

complexity lies not only in the most complex mathematical description of the process, but also in the complexity of its experimental research. Due to the importance of the combustion process in technical devices, coupled with the high cost of full-scale experiments, computer modeling research is being developed.

Application software packages ANSYS CFD, ANSYS Fluent, ANSYS CFX, Star-CD, Flow 3D, Open Foam, Flow Vision, VP2/3, Sigma Flow, FIRE 3D are currently actively used to study and analyze gas dynamics and thermophysical processes in power plants, which work for a variety of simulation conditions using grid methods with improved convergence. The purpose of this work is to simulate the combustion process in the ANSYS Fluent software package. ANSYS Fluent is a full-fledged CFD package, not inferior in functionality to ANSYS CFX, and specializing in modeling multiphase flows and combustion processes. The development of computer technology has made it possible to take engineering calculations to a qualitatively new level. When solving calculation problems, the engineer considers various techniques and approaches that allow obtaining high-quality results in the shortest possible time. Modern practice proves that the use of software systems based on finite difference and finite element methods (FEM) allows one to achieve their goals.

Numerical study of gas combustion is a complex problem in thermophysics, as it requires taking into account a large number of complex interrelated factors and phenomena. Therefore, computational experiment is becoming an increasingly important element in the study of combustion processes and the design of various devices using the combustion process. It is safe to say that his role will continue to increase in the future. In this regard, computational fluid dynamics methods are becoming increasingly widespread in thermophysics, when it becomes possible to optimize an experiment based on its virtual prototype.

Many works are devoted to the study of combustion processes, as well as the substances formed [1-14]. In [3], the authors study the diffusion combustion of methane and propane in a combustion chamber with a square cross-section with fuel supplied through a porous cylinder. The results present the concentration profiles of the fuel components, oxidizer, as well as CO and CO₂. In [4], a numerical and experimental study of the combustion of a partially mixed mixture of methane and air in a cylindrical combustion chamber is carried out. The results present the distributions of temperature and concentrations of components N_2 , O_2 , CH_4 , CO_2 , H_2O , CO , H_2 , OH , NO . The study of diffusion combustion with co-supply of methane and air was carried out in [5, 6], where the results of numerical calculations and experimental data are presented: temperature and concentration profiles CH_4 , CO_2 , H_2O , CO .

The need for efficient and effective mathematical descriptions of turbulent reacting flow systems has led to significant research interest in turbulent models based on turbulent spectrum resolution [7] and combustion models [8] that account for complex chemical reactions without involving too much computational resources. The LES approach [9] is known as one of the most popular turbulent models due to one of its most important features. In it, large-scale turbulent eddies, which dominate turbulent dynamics and motions, are directly resolved by applying a cell size-based filter method [10]. However, this well-known superiority of LES in describing large eddy motions also leads to one drawback of the model: the high computational power required for LES simulations due to the use of fine grid cells to fill the computational domain. Thus, the LES modeling approach is more often used in academia rather than in industry due to the complex and large-scale components that are often required in the latter. On the other hand, in

academia, the focus is on physical phenomena in small- and medium-scale configurations, which allows for the more computationally expensive LES approach.

Due to this drawback of LES, alternative mathematical methods such as single eddy simulation (DES) [11] and scale adaptive simulation (SAS) are attracting more attention from engineers and application engineers due to their lower computational power requirements and their ability to resolve turbulent spectrum. Specifically, the DES method uses a Reynolds Averaging Navier–Stokes (RANS) modeling approach near boundary layer regions and a LES modeling approach in core regions; In addition, the SAS method uses an additional von Kármán length scale to ensure accurate energy distribution across the turbulent spectrum and improve the performance of the RANS model [12]. In fact, DES is often considered a hybrid RANS-LES modeling method of the first generation, and SAS is considered the second generation. This is due to the fact that compared to DES, SAS has two additional advantages that allow it to be quickly adapted to practical problems. First, SAS does not have an explicit local dependence of the grid spacing in each direction, unlike DES [13]. Second, SAS can be easily incorporated into an existing experimentally adapted RANS model.

Article [14] discusses the modeling of pulverized coal combustion processes and presents a methodology for engineering calculations in the BKZ-500 energy boiler using the ANSYS Fluent software package. ANSYS Fluent allows you to simulate the combustion process taking into account turbulence, heat transfer and chemical reactions. To design the computational mesh in the combustion chamber area, the ICEM CFD package was used, which is a mesh preprocessor for ANSYS Fluent. In the area of the combustion chamber of the energy boiler, a hexahedral mesh consisting of 2 million elements was formed. The flow is described by a system of stationary Navier–Stokes equations, conservation of mass and energy, averaged over Reynolds. Turbulent viscosity was calculated using the model $k - \varepsilon$. Radiative heat transfer in a two-phase flow was taken into account within the framework of the P_1 approximation of the spherical harmonics method. The presence of well-studied mechanisms of combustion reactions of certain types of gas allows us to obtain a detailed description of a large number of ongoing processes and a wide range of chemical radicals and reacting components. Among the numerous methods for modeling combustion, the approach based on the proportion of mixing of fuel and oxidizer – the flamelet model – stands out separately. To date, the flamelet model has been seriously modified compared to the original version.

Formulation of the problem

A two-dimensional axisymmetric cylindrical combustion burner was fabricated using ANSYS FLUENT as shown in Fig. 1. The cylindrical burner has a length of 170 cm and a radius of 25 cm. The burner consists of two air and fuel inlet channels. Natural gas (0.232 m³/s) is injected into the burner from a fuel inlet with a radius of 3 cm, and air (0.728 m³/s) enters the chamber through a centered annular channel with a step of 2 cm. The radius of the exit from the chamber is 25 cm. The entire area was prepared with a quadrangular mesh. Four different meshes (i.e., 140k, 335k, 560k, and 650k) were tested in this work.

Figure 1. 2D Flame Burner Geometry

In parallel with the turbulent mixing of the two flows, a chemical reaction occurs between the interacting components - fuel and oxygen from the air. The mixing area gradually expands.

The purpose of this work is to develop a method for calculating the mixing, combustion and propagation of different compositions of combustible mixtures in a cylindrical chamber, which allows for a computational experiment to study heat and mass transfer processes. First of all, it is necessary to select a suitable turbulence model to describe a jet flow with intense chemical transformation.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Mathematical model. Most flows are turbulent in nature, and the state of turbulence during the movement of the medium greatly affects such flow parameters as the transfer of momentum, temperature and concentration of substances in the mixture. The general view of the system of equations describing the turbulent flow of a multicomponent reacting gas is presented below. The Navier-Stokes system of equations, which includes the laws of conservation of mass, momentum, concentration and energy of unsteady spatial flow, is written for a Cartesian coordinate system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho \bar{u}_i) = 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \bar{u}_i) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho \bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\sigma_{ij}) - \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j}, \\ \frac{\partial \rho \bar{h}_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho \bar{u}_i \bar{h}_s}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial t} - \bar{u}_j \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\lambda \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial x_i} \right) = - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\rho (\bar{u}_i \bar{h}_s - \bar{u}_i \bar{h}_s) \right], \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho c_n) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho \bar{u}_i c_n) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\frac{\mu_{eff}}{\sigma_{c_n,eff}} \frac{\partial c_n}{\partial x_i} \right) + S_n. \end{cases}$$

The viscous shear stress tensor is defined as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij} \equiv \left[\mu \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \right] - \frac{2}{3} \mu \frac{\partial \bar{u}_l}{\partial x_l} \delta_{ij}, \quad \tau_{ij} \equiv \overline{\rho u_i u_j} - \rho \bar{u}_i \bar{u}_j,$$

$$\rho \left(\overline{u_i h_s} - \bar{u}_i \bar{h}_s \right) = - \frac{\mu_{SGS} C_p}{Pr_{SGS}} \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial x_j}, \quad S_n = \sum \omega_n,$$

$$-\rho \overline{u'_i u'_j} = \mu_t \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \left(\rho k + \mu_t \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} \right) \delta_{ij};$$

μ_{eff} represents the total dynamic viscosity,

This system is closed by the following dependencies:

$$h = c_p T + c_2 h_2^*, \quad c_p = \sum_{n=1}^N c_{pn} c_n$$

In the process of solving the problem, the following turbulence models are used to describe turbulence.

Modified model $k - \varepsilon$. Unlike work [15], here it is proposed to use a modified model [13-16] to describe turbulent exchange, which contributes to a more adequate description of the heat and mass transfer process:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho k u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_k + G_b - \rho \varepsilon - 2 \rho \varepsilon M_t^2 + S_k, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \varepsilon) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho \varepsilon u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] + \\ \rho C_1 S \varepsilon - \rho C_2 \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k + \sqrt{\nu \varepsilon}} + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} C_{3\varepsilon} G_b + S_\varepsilon. \end{cases}$$

The notation used here is

$$C_1 = \max \left[0.43, \frac{\eta}{\eta + 5} \right], \quad \eta = S \frac{k}{\varepsilon}, \quad S = \sqrt{2 S_{ij} S_{ij}}, \quad \mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon}, \quad C_\mu = \frac{1}{A_0 + A_S \frac{k U^*}{\varepsilon}},$$

$$U^* \equiv \sqrt{S_{ij} S_{ij} + \tilde{\Omega}_{ij} \tilde{\Omega}_{ij}}, \quad \tilde{\Omega}_{ij} = \overline{\Omega}_{ij} - 2 \varepsilon_{ijk} \omega_k, \quad A_S = \sqrt{6} \cos \phi, \quad \phi = \frac{1}{3} \cos^{-1} \left(\sqrt{6} W \right),$$

$$W = \frac{S_{ij}S_{jk}S_{ki}}{\tilde{S}^3}, \quad \tilde{S} = \sqrt{S_{ij}S_{ij}}, \quad S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \right), \quad G_k = -\rho \overline{u'_i u'_j} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial u_i}, \quad S \equiv \sqrt{2S_{ij}S_{ij}},$$

$$G_b = \beta g_i \frac{\mu_i \partial T}{\text{Pr}_i \partial x_i}, \quad \text{Pr}_i = 1/a_i, \quad a_0 = 1/\text{Pr} = k/\mu c_p, \quad \beta = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \right)_p, \quad G_b = -g_i \frac{\mu_i}{\rho \text{Pr}_i} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x_i},$$

$$M_t = \sqrt{\frac{k}{a^2}}, \quad a = \sqrt{\gamma RT}.$$

Empirical constants $k-\varepsilon$ models take standard values: $C_{1\varepsilon} = 1.44$, $C_2 = 1.9$, $\sigma_k = 1.0$, $\sigma_\varepsilon = 1.2$, $A_0 = 4.04$.

Spalart-Allmaras model. This model belongs to the class of one-parameter linear turbulence models. Here only one additional differential equation appears for calculating the kinematic coefficient of eddy viscosity. This low Reynolds turbulence model, which describes the entire flow region, is given by the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \tilde{v}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho \tilde{v} u_i) =$$

$$G_v + \frac{1}{\sigma_{\tilde{v}}} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left\{ (\mu + \rho \tilde{v}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x_j} \right\} + C_{b2\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial x_j} \right)^2 \right] - C_{w1\rho} f_w \left(\frac{\tilde{v}}{d} \right)^2 + S_{\tilde{v}}.$$

Turbulent eddy viscosity is calculated by the formula: $\mu_t = \rho \tilde{v} f_{v1}$, additional definitions are given by the following dependencies: $f_{v1} = \frac{\chi^3}{\chi^3 + C_{v1}^3}$, $\chi = \frac{\tilde{v}}{\nu}$, $\tilde{S} \equiv S + \frac{\nu}{\kappa^2 d^2} f_{v2}$,

$$f_{v2} = 1 - \frac{\chi}{1 + \chi f_{v1}}, \quad S \equiv \sqrt{2\Omega_{ij}\Omega_{ij}}, \quad \Omega_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right), \quad S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \right),$$

$$f_w = g \left[\frac{1 + C_{w3}^6}{g^6 + C_{w3}^6} \right]^{1/6}, \quad r = \frac{\tilde{v}}{S \kappa^2 d^2},$$

and the closure constants for the model are: $C_{prod} = 2.0$, $C_{b1} = 0.1355$, $C_{b2} = 0.622$, $\sigma_{\tilde{v}} = \frac{2}{3}$, $C_{v1} = 7.1$, $C_{w1} = \frac{C_{b1}}{\kappa^2} + \frac{(1 + C_{b2})}{\sigma_{\tilde{v}}}$, $C_{w2} = 0.3$, $C_{w3} = 2.0$, $\kappa = 0.4187$.

Standard model $k-\varepsilon$.

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho k u_i) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_k + G_b - \rho \varepsilon - Y_M + S_k, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \varepsilon) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho \varepsilon u_i) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right] + \\ &+ C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} (G_k + C_{3\varepsilon} G_b) - C_{2\varepsilon\rho} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} + S_\varepsilon. \end{aligned} \right.$$

Turbulent eddy viscosity is calculated by the formula: $\mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon}$, closure constants for standard $k - \varepsilon$ models: $C_{1\varepsilon} = 1.44$, $C_{2\varepsilon} = 1.92$, $C_\mu = 0.09$, $\sigma_k = 1.0$, $\sigma_\varepsilon = 1.3$.

RNG model $k - \varepsilon$ [15].

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho k u_i) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\alpha_k \mu_{eff} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_k + G_b - \rho \varepsilon - Y_M + S_k, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \varepsilon) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho \varepsilon u_i) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\alpha_\varepsilon \mu_{eff} \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial x_j} \right) + \\ &+ C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} (G_k + C_{3\varepsilon} G_b) - C_{2\varepsilon\rho} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k} - R_\varepsilon + S_\varepsilon. \end{aligned} \right.$$

Turbulent eddy viscosity is calculated by the formula: $\mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon}$, closure constants for

RNG $k - \varepsilon$ model: : $C_\mu = 0.0845$, $R_\varepsilon = \frac{C_\mu \rho \eta^3 (1 - \eta / \eta_0) \varepsilon^2}{1 + \beta \eta^3} \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k}$, $\eta \equiv S k / \varepsilon$, $\eta_0 = 4.38$, $\beta = 0.012$, $\eta \approx 3.0$, $C_{2\varepsilon}^* \approx 2.0$, $C_{1\varepsilon} = 1.42$, $C_{2\varepsilon} = 1.68$.

Model $k - \omega$ This model is historically the very first high-Reynolds model with two differential equations [15]. Does not contain terms reflecting the influence of molecular viscosity on turbulence. Nowadays it is rarely used.

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho k u_i) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_k - \rho \beta^* f_{\beta^*} k \omega + S_k, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \omega) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho \omega u_i) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left[\Gamma_\omega \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right] + G_\omega - \rho \beta f_\beta \omega^2 + S_\omega. \end{aligned} \right.$$

Turbulent eddy viscosity is calculated by the formula: $\mu_t = \alpha^* \frac{\rho k}{\omega}$, model constants are defined as a function $\Gamma_k = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k}$, $\Gamma_\omega = \mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\omega}$, $\alpha^* = \alpha_\infty^* \left(\frac{\alpha_0^* + \text{Re}_t / R_k}{1 + \text{Re}_t / R_k} \right)$, $\text{Re}_t = \frac{\rho k}{\mu \omega}$, $G_k = -\rho \overline{u'_i u'_j} \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i}$, $\Omega_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right)$, $G_\omega = \alpha \frac{\omega}{k} G_k$, $\alpha = \frac{\alpha_\infty}{\alpha^*} \left(\frac{\alpha_0 + \text{Re}_t / R_\omega}{1 + \text{Re}_t / R_\omega} \right)$, $\chi_k \equiv \frac{1}{\omega^3} \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j}$, $\beta^* = \beta_i^* [1 + \zeta^* F(M_t)]$, closure constants for $k - \omega$ models: $\alpha_0^* = \frac{\beta_i}{3}$, $R_k = 6$, $\beta_i = 0.072$, $\alpha^* = \alpha_\infty^* = 1$, $R_\omega = 2.95$, $\alpha = \alpha_\infty = 1$, $\beta_i^* = \beta_\infty^* \left(\frac{4/15 + (\text{Re}_t / R_\beta)^4}{1 + (\text{Re}_t / R_\beta)^4} \right)$, $\zeta^* = 1.5$, $R_\beta = 8$, $\beta_\infty^* = 0.09$, $\chi_\omega = \left| \frac{\Omega_{ij} \Omega_{ij} S_{ij}}{(\beta_\infty^* \omega)^3} \right|$, $\beta = \beta_i \left[1 - \frac{\beta_i^*}{\beta_i} \zeta^* F(M_t) \right]$, $M_t^2 \equiv \frac{2k}{a^2}$, $M_{t0} = 0.25$, $a = \sqrt{\gamma RT}$, $\alpha_\infty^* = 1$, $\alpha_\infty = 0.52$, $\alpha_0 = \frac{1}{9}$, $\beta_\infty^* = 0.09$, $\beta_i = 0.072$, $R_\beta = 8$, $R_k = 6$, $R_\omega = 2.95$, $\zeta^* = 1.5$, $M_{t0} = 0.25$, $\sigma_k = 2.0$, $\sigma_\omega = 2.0$.

The system of Navier–Stokes equations, reduced to two nonlinear diffusion equations that take into account fluctuations in the average velocity of turbulent flows, is a family of models $k - \varepsilon$ and $k - \omega$, where k – mass density of turbulent energy, ε – its dissipation rate; ω – rate of energy dissipation per unit volume and time. A special feature of this system is that its solution is cascaded, which is most convenient for use in software packages for modeling processes in cylindrical coordinates.

Here and further u, v – averaged longitudinal and transverse (radial) components of the velocity vector ($m s^{-1}$) in cylindrical coordinates; ρ, T – density ($kg m^{-3}$) and absolute temperature (K) of the gas mixture; P – hydrostatic pressure (Pa); Pr, Sc_n – turbulent analogues of the Prandtl and Schmidt numbers; C_n – mass concentration of the n th gas component in the mixture ($kg kg^{-1}$); ω_n – mass rate of formation or disappearance of the gas component ($kg m^{-3} s^{-1}$); $c_p = \sum_{n=1}^N c_{pn} c_n$ и c_{pn} – heat capacity of the gas mixture and the n th component at constant pressure ($J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$); h_n^* – calorific value of the n th component ($J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$); ν, ν_t – kinematic coefficients of laminar and turbulent viscosity ($m^2 s^{-1}$);

The gas mixture is assumed to be perfect, so its state satisfies the Mendeleev-Clapeyron equation:

$$p = \rho R_0 T / m.$$

Combustion model

The issue of modeling sources in the equations of energy and transfer of concentrations associated with chemical reactions occurring during the combustion process deserves special attention

The Arrhenius rate coefficient of the direct reaction is determined as follows [15-20]:

$$\tilde{\omega}_2 = -A_{fk} n_1 n_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_k}{R_0 T}\right),$$

where A_{fk} – pre exponential factor; E_k – activation energy.

Methane is considered as a combustible gas, the one-stage combustion kinetics of which in air is given through the stoichiometric equation [17-19]:

where $\nu'_{CH_4} = 1$; $\nu'_{O_2} = 2$; $\nu''_{CO_2} = 1$; $\nu''_{H_2O} = 2$.

The rate of the combustion reaction of methane with oxygen in the equation of conservation of fuel mass, according to proposals in [15], has the form:

$$\tilde{\omega}_2 = -A_{r1} \frac{c_1 c_2 \bar{\rho}^2}{\bar{u}} \exp(-A_{r2} / T),$$

where $A_{r1} = 8.6 \cdot 10^9$, $\frac{E_a}{R} = 18,05 = A_{r2}$.

Calculation algorithm

The equations described above are integrated using the finite volume method in ANSYS Fluent. Convective and diffusion fluxes are calculated with second-order approximation. Due to the fact that all the problems simulated below are quasi-stationary, the first order of approximation in time is used. The velocity and pressure fields are connected using the PISO algorithm. Depending on the chosen combustion model, solution algorithms have distinctive features.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The problem is solved in a two-dimensional formulation; cylindricity is taken into account using a computational mesh constructed in the form of a sector. To simplify the presentation, in the section describing the boundary conditions, here and below, the parameters are given immediately for both the flamelet model and the kinetic reaction rate models.

Boundary conditions for the computational domain are specified as follows [15-20]:

$$r = 0: \frac{\partial F}{\partial r} = 0, \quad F = \{U, T, c_i, k, \varepsilon\}, \quad \mathcal{G} = 0;$$

$$r = R_0 : \frac{\partial F}{\partial r} = 0, \quad F = \{T, c_i, k, \varepsilon\}, \quad \mathcal{G} = 0, \quad u = 0;$$

$$x = 0 : r < R_2 : \quad \mathcal{G} = 0, \quad u = 82 \text{ m/s}, \quad T = 300 \text{ K}, \quad c_2 = 1;$$

$$x = 0 : R_2 < r < R_3 : \quad \frac{\partial F}{\partial x} = 0, \quad F = \{T, c_i, k, \varepsilon\}, \quad u = \mathcal{G} = 0;$$

$$x = 0 : R_3 < x < R_4 : \quad \mathcal{G} = 0, \quad u = 0.6 \text{ m/s}, \quad T = 300 \text{ K}, \quad c = 1.$$

The computational grid is condensed in logarithmic form. Grid convergence was studied on various finite-volume grids with non-uniform spacing: (No. 1), (No. 2), (No. 3). Significant quantitative differences in the results are observed in calculations using grids No. 1 and No. 2. However, when calculating on grids No. 2 and No. 3, the differences in the distribution of parameters are small. Therefore, the main calculations are carried out on a grid.

Below we compare the calculation results based on the presented turbulence models with experimental data from [15]

In Fig. Figure 2 shows the curves of the axial temperature of the gas mixture, and Fig. 3 mass concentration of combustion components CO₂. As can be seen from the figures, the modified *k* – ε The turbulence model gives results close to the experiment.

In Fig. Figure 4 shows the axial distribution of longitudinal velocity. The abrupt change in velocity at the beginning of the computational domain is due to the presence of a nozzle protrusion.

Figure 2. Axial temperature

Figure 3. Mass concentration of CO₂ combustion components

Figure 4. The axial distribution of longitudinal velocity is shown

Figure 5. Static temperature

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained in the article demonstrate the possibility of using the ANSYS Fluent software package to effectively calculate the gas combustion process in a power boiler. Thus, according to the results of a comparative analysis of experimental and program packages of five turbulence models, the calculated values of axial temperature and carbon dioxide concentration presented in Fig. 2 and fig. 3, it can be noted that the maximum difference between the values of mathematical modeling and experiment does not exceed 10% [15].

Analyzing the results, one can notice that the modified model coincides more qualitatively with the experiment than the other four turbulence models.

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